
Theoretical study of 1, 3-Dipolar Cycloaddition Reaction of Benzyl Azide and its Derivatives with Cinnamic Acid M062X/6-31 g(d)

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Abstract The 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition of the Benzyl azide and its derivatives(-H, 2-Cl, 3-Cl, 3-OCH₃, 4-OCH₃, 4-NO₂, 2,6-Cl) with Cinnamic acid was studied theoretically using Density Functional Theory (DFT) MO62X with the basic set 6-31g(d) with solvents: water, dimethyl sulfoxide(DMSO), Acetonitrile, Ethanol, Tetrahydrofuran (THF), Dimethyl Ether and Heptane. We have identified thermodynamic properties and kinetic factors using Polarization Continuous Method PCM in the level of theory M062X/6-31 g (d).

The results of the level of theory M062X/6-31g (d) indicate that the one, 3-dipolar cycloaddition of the Benzyl azide carried out spontaneously in the gas state to form several stable energy products. P1 and P2 are most stable, but all the reactions are very slow and one of the products P1 is more spontaneous than P2 but the formation reaction of P2 is faster.

On the other hand, it is found that solvents to have no actual effects on the rates of these reactions but it was observed that TS-P1 transition state energy for all substitutes was lower than TS-P2 transition state energy.

Keywords 1,3-Dipolar Cycloaddition, Density-functional theory (DFT), Basic Set 6-31g (d), Benzyl azide.

Introduction

Azides are crucial compounds due to its bioapplications [1], azide derivatives were used in vulcanization [2]; inter polymer entanglement [3], dyes, medication, insecticide [4], tire adhesives and plastics [1]. The synthesis of one, 2, 3-triazole through 1, 3 dipolar cycloaddition is one of the most useful synthetic applications [2], more useful than azides [3, 4]. 1,2,3-triazole is an item of crucial heterocyclic compound given its importance, as an intermediate chemical [5], in the synthetic of pharmaceutical and its preparations [6].

Lately, the 1,3dipolar cycloaddition of the Benzyl azide with cinnamic acid was studied experimentally not theoretically. Researchers could not recognize the primary product through the spectral analysis of this product [7].

The 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition of the Benzyl azide with cinnamic acid studied experimentally and theoretically using the level of theory B3LYP [8, 9].

Materials and Methods of Research

We will use MO62X Of density functional theory (DFT) using 6-31g(d) to identify thermodynamic properties and kinetic factors of the considered reactants [10-19]. We used GAUSSIAN-09 software to achieve theoretical calculations [13].

The Importance of the Research

1. Study the mechanism of reaction of azide and its derivatives with cinnamic acid theoretically (Figure 1).
 2. Determine the thermodynamic and kinetic properties for each phase in the reaction mechanism using some methods in Density Functional Theory DFT.
 3. Examine the effects of substitutes in the thermodynamic and kinetic properties of the reaction.
 4. Show the effects of solvents in thermodynamic properties and kinetic factors of the examined reactions.
- The importance of the research lies in the interpretation of the intractable experimental results, especially when the reaction leads to many products such as cycloaddition reactants (1, 3).

Calculations

The geometric structure of the reaction components and standard thermodynamic properties and its energy have been identified using the theory MO62X with the basic set 6-31g(d) in the gas state and with different solvents. The simple mathematical way to calculate the enthalpy or Gibbs free energy requires first to calculate enthalpy or Gibbs free energy then the total and difference. For example to calculate enthalpy of reaction:

$$\Delta_r H^\circ(298.15) = \sum_{\text{products}} \Delta_f H^\circ(298.15) - \sum_{\text{reactants}} \Delta_f H^\circ(298.15)$$

That in turn demands electrical energy E_0 for reaction components and its standard enthalpy H_{corr} and limitations of correcting atomic energies that form the molecules engaging and resulting from the interaction [14]. This correction would not have been the same in both sides of a chemical reaction. Therefore the result of the difference in the former relation is removed. The knowledge of is required $(E_0 + H_{\text{corr}})$ or $(E_0 + G_{\text{corr}})$ only to estimate the enthalpy or Gibbs free energy respectively. Consequently, the former relation becomes the following formul:

$$\Delta_r H^\circ(298.15) = \sum_{\text{products}} (E_0 + H_{\text{corr}}) - \sum_{\text{reactants}} (E_0 + H_{\text{corr}})$$

Similarly, the phrase is written $\Delta_r G^\circ(298.15)$. Transition State theory (TS) [24] assumes that the speed of the reaction is related to the formation of this state which is at the maximum point of the curve energy starting with the reactants to the products.

The transition theory is studied as a nearly balanced state with the reactive materials. Thus the speed of the reaction can be identified with the following relation:

$$k(T) = \frac{k_B T}{h} \exp(-\Delta^\# G / RT)$$

k_B Boltzman constant, h Blank constant and $\Delta^\# G$ represent the change in Gibbs free energy due to the formation of transition state; that $\Delta^\# G = \Delta G_{\text{TS}} - \Delta G_{\text{reactants}}$ R gas constant, T thermodynamic temperature and for stable compounds $\Delta^\# G = \Delta^\# H - T\Delta^\# S$ in this way, we can estimate activation energy through the following formula:

$$E_a = \Delta^\# H + nRT$$

$\Delta^\# H$ Represents the enthalpy of transition state and n represents rotational degrees of freedom [15].

Outcomes and Discussion:

Annulation of Benzyl azide and some of its derivatives with cinnamic acid was studied in this research according to the mechanism described in figure (1) using M062X Density Functional Theory (DFT) and using the basic set 6-

Figure 3: Engineering structures for the resulting materials

Table 1: Energies in one (hartree), and the energy differences for the four potential flight products in one kJ mol⁻¹ estimated by the theoretical level M062X / 6-31g (d)

Products	P1	P3	P2	P4
E(hartree)	-933.3906367	-933.3893689	-933.3892942	-933.3890503
ΔE (kJ mol ⁻¹)	0	3.33	0	0.64

We notice in table (1) that P1 product, resulting from phase one is more stable than P3 product by about 33.3 kJ mol⁻¹ while p2 product resulting from phase 2 is more stable than p4 by about 0.64 kJ mol⁻¹. Therefore, we will define thermodynamic properties and kinetic factors of the reaction resulting in P1, P2 and the transition states TS-P1 and TS-P2 figure (4).

Figure 4: The engineering architecture corresponding to the TS-P1 and TS-P2 transitions defined with the theoretical level M062X / 6-31g (d)

It was noticed for synthesis reaction for all substitutes of Benzyl azide studied with cinnamic acid that the products P1 and P2 are more stable than P3 and P4 formed from 1 and 2 phases respectively in the gas state.

Thermodynamic properties and kinetic factors of Benzyl azide reaction and its derivatives with cinnamic acid in the gas state

Table (2) shows thermodynamic properties and kinetic factors for Benzyl azide and some of its derivatives with cinnamic acid in the gas state at the temperature 298.15 k defined by the level of theory M06-2X/6-31g (d). Figure (5) represents the changes in Gibbs free energy along the course of interaction for Benzyl azide interaction with cinnamic acid in the gas state.

Table 2

bstSuitutes	H	4-NO ₂	2-Cl	3-Cl	2,6-Cl	3-OCH ₃	4-OCH ₃
$\Delta^{\#}G(\text{TS-P1})$	123.49	126.29	125.58	122.43	127.72	124.97	124.73
$\Delta^{\#}G(\text{TS-P2})$	121.74	112.74	110.43	114.81	111.18	118.53	119.38
$\Delta_r G_{P1}$	-74.49	-76.53	-72.94	-73.02	-72.14	-70.96	-71.17
$\Delta_r G_{P2}$	-70.23	-69.02	-67.09	-73.04	-60.07	-65.45	-66.63
$E_a(\text{P1})$	65.98	68.16	72.23	66.51	71.98	66.80	67.10
$E_a(\text{P2})$	66.30	61.63	60.68	62.74	60.51	63.77	64.70
$k_{P1} \times 10^{10}$	14.4	4.67	6.19	22.1	2.62	7.95	8.73
$k_{P2} \times 10^{10}$	29.2	1100	2800	479	2070	107	75.6

Solvents Effect

Solvents show great effects in the kinetic factors of the reactions especially heterogeneous reactions. In this research we used various solvents: water, methyl sulfoxide (DMSO), acetonitrile, ethanol, tetrahydrofuran (THF), dimethyl ether and heptane.

We identified thermodynamic properties and the kinetic factors using (PCM) in the level of theory M06-2X/6-31g (d). Table (3) shows the calculation results while figure (6) shows that Gibbs free energy in the transition states TS-P1 and TS-P2 change with the relative static permittivity of the solvent in relation to Benzyl azide reaction.

Table 3: Gibbs free energy and the kinetic factors of Benzyl azide with cinnamic acid change with the solvent calculated using the level of theory M06-2X/6-31g(d) in unit kj mol .constant reaction rate k indicates the unit l mol s . Represents relative static permittivity

	Gas	Heptane	Diethyl ether	THF	Ethanol	Acetonitrile	DMSO	Water
Σ	> 1	1.91	4.24	7.43	20.49	35.69	46.83	78.36
$\Delta G^\ddagger(\text{TS-P1})$	123.49	124.36	124.76	124.81	124.77	124.76	124.75	124.74
$\Delta G^\ddagger(\text{TS-P2})$	121.74	122.37	122.78	122.93	123.06	123.08	123.09	123.10
$\Delta rG(\text{P1})$	-74.49	-75.19	-75.81	-76.12	-76.47	-76.53	-76.56	-76.60
$\Delta rG(\text{P2})$	-70.23	-71.67	-72.89	-73.43	-73.10	-74.08	-74.12	-74.18
$E_a(\text{P1})$	65.98	66.86	67.26	67.31	67.27	67.26	67.25	67.24
$E_a(\text{P2})$	66.30	66.90	67.34	67.49	67.62	67.64	67.64	67.65
$k_{\text{P1}}(\times 10^9)$	1.44	1.01	0.86	0.85	0.86	0.86	0.87	0.87
$k_{\text{P2}}(\times 10^9)$	2.92	2.29	1.92	1.80	1.71	1.70	1.70	1.69

Figures from (6) to (12) show that Gibbs free energy in the transition states TS-P1 and TS-P2 changes with the relative static permittivity of solvents in relation to studied Benzyl azide substitutes .

Figure 6: Gibbs free energy change for TS-P1 and TS-P2 transitional states by solvent change based on the results of the theoretical level M06-2X / 6-31g (d) for Benzyl azide increased reaction with cinnamic acid

Figure 7: Gibbs free energy change for TS-P1 and TS-P2 transitional states with solvent change based on the results of the theoretical level M06-2X / 6-31g (d) for a 4-nitro-aryslyated reaction reaction with cinnamic acid

Figure 8: Gibbs free energy change for TS-P1 and TS-P2 transitional states with solvent change based on the results of the theoretical level M06-2X / 6-31g (d) for a 2-chloro- Benzyl increased reaction with cinnamic acid

Figure 9: Gibbs free energy change for TS-P1 and TS-P2 transitional states with solvent change based on the results of the theoretical level M06-2X / 6-31g (d) for a 3-chloro- Benzyl increased reaction with cinnamic acid

Figure 10: Gibbs free energy change for TS-P1 and TS-P2 transitional states by solvent change based on the results of the theoretical level level M06-2X / 6-31g (d) for the flight reaction of 2, 6-chlorine Benzyl increased with cinnamic aci

Figure 11: Gibbs free energy change for TS-P1 and TS-P2 transitional states by solvent change based on the results of the theoretical level M06-2X / 6-31g (d) for a 3-methoxy- Benzyl increased reaction with cinnamic acid

Figure 12: Gibbs free energy change for TS-P1 and TS-P2 transitional states by solvent change based on the results of the theoretical level M06-2X / 6-31g (d) for a 4-methoxy- Benzyl reaction with cinnamic acid

Conclusions and recommendations

The level of theory M062x indicates that all the studied cycloaddition reactions are spontaneous in relation to the products P1 and P2 but the formation reaction of P2 is faster than P1 in the gas state.

Solvents show negative effects in the rate of formation reaction P1 .In other words cycloaddition reactants of Benzyl azide and its studied substitutes resulting in the formation of P1 and P2 in the gas state are faster with the solvents.

It is noted from the results of the level of theory MO6-2X / 6-31g (d), that the reaction with the substitute 4-No2, is more spontaneous compared to the substitute H in relation to the formation of P1 product while, the reaction, with the substitute 3-Cl, is more spontaneous compared to the substitute H in relation to the formation of P2 product.

The results of the level of theory MO6-2X/6-31g(d) indicate that the reaction with 2-Cl is faster in relation to the formation of P2 product compared to the substitute H when the substitute 3-Cl increases the speed of formation reaction P2 compared to the substitute H .

Following the level of theory results M06-2X/6-31g (d), constant reaction rate (1, 3) to the formation of p1 and P2 is from status 10⁻⁷ -10⁻¹⁰ based on the nature of the substitute; it is the maximum in case of the substitute 2-Cl for the formation of P2.

It is advisable to use the level of theory M06-2X/6-31g (d) to estimate thermodynamic properties and kinetic factors for other similar reactants for it gives logical results and it takes a short time.

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